

Transparency Material for the Project Proposal
“Data Quality of Textual, User-Generated Content (DQUGC)”

Table T1. DQ dimensions and respective selected approaches for assessing and improving DQ in UGC (starting from 2019, as earlier approaches are already discussed in the previous project proposal DQNGI, and omitting own work, which is discussed in the proposal DQUGC)

DQ Dimension	Literature	Description	Limitations
Accuracy / Currency	Caramancion, 2023	Assessment of the accuracy of facts using large language models (LLMs)	- Limited accuracy regarding the classification of facts - Limited interpretability of the results
	Hao et al., 2020; Meng et al., 2020	Assessment of currency based on time since creation or last update	- No consideration of textual semantics - Limited interpretability of the results
	Kiefer, 2019	Assessment of the accuracy of texts based on lexical features (e.g. percentage of spelling mistakes) and performance of standard text analysis modules	- No consideration of textual semantics - Limited interpretability of the results
Completeness	Luitel et al., 2024	Improvement of the completeness of requirements for systems and software using LLMs	- Approach limited to the chosen use case
	Mylavarapu, 2020; Mylavarapu et al., 2023	Assessment of the consistency of texts by comparing dependency graphs of similar texts	- Approaches limited to situations in which quality-assured texts for the comparison are available - Limited interpretability of the results
Consistency	Jo et al., 2020	Assessment of the consistency of texts based on graphs and Word2Vec	- Approach limited to situations in which quality-assured texts for the comparison are available - Limited interpretability of the results
Identity	Elazar et al., 2023	Identification of duplicated textual documents based on MD5 hashes	- Approaches limited to duplicates with identical hashes or authors (no semantic duplicates) - Limited interpretability of the results
	António et al., 2023	Identification of duplicate reviews based on associated author	
	Ding et al., 2024; Li et al., 2020	Identification of duplicates based on LLMs	- No consideration of duplicates' causes - Limited interpretability of the results

Table T2. Groups of approaches and respective selected approaches for the propagation of DQ-annotated input data (again starting from 2019 and omitting own work)

Group	Literature	Description	Limitations
Function approximation-based approaches	Daruna et al., 2023; Monchot et al., 2023; Wright et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2019; Zhang & Shin, 2021	- Approximate (or directly assume) DQ annotations with parametrical probability distributions—typically only Gaussian distributions—to facilitate their propagation	- DQ annotations cannot be approximated well by parametrical probability distributions - Propagation results in substantial errors
Sample-based approaches	Ji et al., 2019; Jia et al., 2019; Pilipovsky et al., 2023; Truong, 2021	- Map a set of samples through the model - “Lightweight” approaches to reduce computational costs	- Propagation prohibitively costly or conducted on very limited information - Propagation is infeasible or results in substantial errors

References

- António, N., Correia, M. B., & Ribeiro, F. P. (2023). Understanding the impacts and motivations of duplicate reviews on Tripadvisor. *Cuadernos De Turismo*(52), 219–238.
- Caramancion, K. M. (2023). News Verifiers Showdown: A Comparative Performance Evaluation of ChatGPT 3.5, ChatGPT 4.0, Bing AI, and Bard in News Fact-Checking. In *2023 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF)*.
- Daruna, A., Gong, Y., Rajvanshi, A., Chiu, H.-P., & Yao, Y. (2023). Uncertainty Propagation through Trained Deep Neural Networks Using Factor Graphs. *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2312.05946*.
- Ding, H., Dai, C., Wu, Y., Ma, W., & Zhou, H. (2024). SETEM: Self-ensemble training with Pre-trained Language Models for Entity Matching. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 293, 111708.
- Elazar, Y., Bhagia, A., Magnusson, I., Ravichander, A., Schwenk, D., Suhr, A., Walsh, P., Groeneveld, D., Soldaini, L., Singh, S., & others (2023). What's In My Big Data? *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2310.20707*.
- Hao, S., Chai, C., Li, G., Tang, N., Wang, N., & Yu, X. (2020). Outdated Fact Detection in Knowledge Bases. In *Proc. International Conference on Data Engineering* (pp. 1890–1893).
- Ji, W., Ren, Z., & Law, C. (2019). *Uncertainty Propagation in Deep Neural Network Using Active Subspace*. arXiv.
- Jia, X. Y., Jiang, C., Fu, C. M., Ni, B. Y., Wang, C. S., & Ping, M. H. (2019). Uncertainty Propagation Analysis by an Extended Sparse Grid Technique. *Frontiers of Mechanical Engineering*, 14(1), 33–46.
- Jo, H., Kim, J., Porras, P., Yegneswaran, V., & Shin, S. (2020). GapFinder: Finding inconsistency of security information from unstructured text. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, 16, 86–99.
- Kiefer, C. (2019). Quality indicators for text data. In *BTW 2019-Workshopband*. Symposium conducted at the meeting of Gesellschaft für Informatik, Bonn.
- Li, Y., Li, J., Suhara, Y., Doan, A., & Tan, W.-C. (2020). Deep entity matching with pre-trained language models. *Proc. VLDB Endow.*, 14(1), 50–60.
- Luitel, D., Hassani, S., & Sabetzadeh, M. (2024). Improving requirements completeness: Automated assistance through large language models. *Requirements Engineering*, 29(1), 73–95.
- Meng, Y., Yang, N., Qian, Z., & Zhang, G. (2020). What makes an online review more helpful: an interpretation framework using XGBoost and SHAP values. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(3), 466–490.
- Monchot, P., Coquelin, L., Petit, S. J., Marmin, S., Le Pennec, E., & Fischer, N. (2023). Input uncertainty propagation through trained neural networks. In *Proc. International Conference on Machine Learning*.
- Mylavarapu, G. (2020). *Context-aware quality assessment of structured and unstructured data* [, Oklahoma State University]. BibTeX.
- Mylavarapu, G., Viswanathan, K. A., & Thomas, J. (2023). Context-aware automated quality assessment of textual data. *International Journal of Business Intelligence and Data Mining*, 22(4), 451–469.
- Pilipovsky, J., Sivaramakrishnan, V., Oishi, M., & Tsiotras, P. (2023). Probabilistic verification of ReLU neural networks via characteristic functions. In *Proc. Learning for Dynamics and Control Conference*.
- Truong, D. (2021). Estimating the Impact of COVID-19 on Air Travel in the Medium and Long Term Using Neural Network and Monte Carlo Simulation. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 96, 102126.
- Wright, O., Nakahira, Y., & Moura, J. M. F. (2024). An Analytic Solution to Covariance Propagation in Neural Networks. In *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*. Symposium conducted at the meeting of PMLR.
- Wu, A., Nowozin, S., Meeds, E., Turner, R. E., Hernández-Lobato, J. M., & Gaunt, A. L. (2019). Deterministic Variational Inference for Robust Bayesian Neural Networks. In *7th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2019, New Orleans, LA, USA, May 6-9, 2019*. OpenReview.net. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=B1108oAct7>
- Zhang, B., & Shin, Y. C. (2021). An Adaptive Gaussian Mixture Method for Nonlinear Uncertainty Propagation in Neural Networks. *Neurocomputing*, 458, 170–183.